

Catalytic aerobic oxidative coupling of some simple phenols and natural phenanthrols with CuCl(OH).TMEDA

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Aerobic oxidative coupling of phenol, catechol, resorcinol and pyrogallol with CuCl(OH).TMEDA as catalyst affords 2',4'-dihydroxybiphenyl (1a), 3,3',4,4'-tetrahydroxybiphenyl (2a), 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxybiphenyl (3a) and 2,2',4,6'-tetrahydroxybiphenyl (4a) and 2',3,3',4,4',5-hexahydroxybiphenyl (5a), respectively, in moderate yields. Similar catalytic aerobic oxidative coupling of the naturally occurring phenanthrols, nudol (6a) [2,7-dihydroxy-3,4-dimethoxyphenanthrene], 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene (6b) and cirrhoptalin (7) [7-hydroxy-4-methoxy-2,3-methylenedioxyphenanthrene] with the same reagent gives the corresponding 1,1'-biphenanthryls 8a and 8c and the 8,8'-biphenanthryl 9a, respectively, in very good yields. All these reactions exhibit a high degree of regioselectivity.

Oxidative coupling of phenols is an old reaction¹ which provides simple method for making an aryl-aryl bond. But initially the reaction failed to create any significant impact as a good synthetic method due to relatively poor yields owing to extensive polymerization and lack of regioselectivity. Later the reaction evoked renewed interest for the following reasons. The biogenesis of a large number of polyphenolics and a variety of tetrahydroisoquinoline alkaloids was assumed² to involve enzymatic oxidative phenol-coupling reaction as an obligatory step and this led to extensive studies³⁻¹⁹ with several oxidants, viz. FeCl₃⁵, alkaline K₃[Fe(CN)₆]^{3,6}, [Fe^{III}(DMF)₃Cl₂][Fe^{III}Cl₄]⁷, [Fe^{III}(bipy)₃](ClO₄)₃⁸, MnO₂⁹, Mn^{III}-tris-acetyl acetonate (MTA)¹⁰, Ag₂CO₃, AgNO₃ on celite¹¹, Ag₂O¹², VCl₄¹³, VOCl₃^{13,14}, VOF₃¹⁵, Ti-tris-trifluoroacetate (TIFA)¹⁶, ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN)¹⁷, diacetoxyiodobenzene (DAIB)¹⁸, Cu^{II}-amine complexes¹⁹ and several other oxidants, resulting in the biomimetic synthesis of a fairly large number of natural products and their synthetic analogues, *albeit* in poor to moderate yields in most cases. More recently, this reaction has been used to prepare axially chiral biaryls which are widely used in organic synthesis as chirality inducers²⁰. Till the end of 1980's the aforesaid oxidants were extensively used for oxidative phenol-coupling reactions. But no significant breakthrough could be made particularly in regard to the yields and regioselectivity of the reaction. In early 1990's we developed a novel reagent²¹ which consists of phosphomolybdic acid (PMA) adsorbed on silica gel for oxidative phenol-coupling reaction. Using this reagent regioselective biomimetic synthesis of several naturally occurring phenolic biphenanthryls and some of their structural analogues were achieved²¹ from

their respective phenolic monomers in high yields (80–95%) 2-Naphthol was almost quantitatively converted to its 1,1'-dimer with this reagent²¹. But with simple phenols it did not work well. This reagent was found to be highly satisfactory, if the site of dimerization is doubly activated by electron-donating groups like OH and or OMe. Electron-withdrawing groups tend to retard the reaction. More recently Noji *et al.*²² also reported a very elegant method for catalytic aerobic oxidative coupling of phenols with CuCl(OH).TMEDA [TMEDA = *N,N'*-tetramethylethylenediamine]. Using this reagent they were able to convert²² 2-naphthol and four of its derivatives to the corresponding 1,1'-dimers in very high yields (90–96%). 9-Phenanthrol was also converted to the corresponding 10,10'-dimer in 79% yield with this reagent²². As part of our on-going general programme of research on oxidative phenol-coupling reactions^{21,23}, we have applied this reagent for oxidative coupling of phenol, catechol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and the naturally occurring monomeric phenolic phenanthrene derivatives, nudol (6a)²¹, 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene (6b)²¹ and cirrhoptalin (7)²¹. We report here the results of the above reactions.

Results and Discussion

Treatment of phenol with CuCl(OH).TMEDA afforded the unsymmetrical biphenyl derivative 1a in about 30% yield. It showed strong absorption at $\nu_{\max}$ 3400 cm⁻¹ for phenolic hydroxyl groups. The ¹H NMR spectrum of 1a showed signals at δ 7.97 and 7.99 (each 1H, s, disappeared on deuterium exchange) for two phenolic hydroxyl protons. The presence of two phenolic hydroxyl groups in

1a : R = H
1b : R = Ac

2a : R = H
2b : R = Ac

5a : R = H
5b : R = Ac

3a

4a

6a : R¹=H
6b : R¹=OMe

8a : R¹=R²=R³=H
8b : R¹=R³=Ac, R²=H
8c : R¹=R³=H, R²=OMe
8d : R¹=R³=Ac, R²=OMe

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9a : R = H
9b : R = Ac

1a was also confirmed by the formation of its diacetyl derivative 1b. The ¹H NMR spectrum of 1a also showed signals for eight aromatic protons, four of which appeared at δ 6.68 and 7.27 (each 2H, d *J* 8.13 Hz) exhibiting an A₂X₂ type of splitting pattern of a *p*-disubstituted benzene moiety and were attributed to H-2, H-6 and H-3, H-5, respectively, of 1a. The remaining four aromatic protons of 1a appeared at δ 7.15 (1H, app.t), 6.87 (2H, ill-res.m) and 7.04 (1H, ill-res.d, *J* 8.1 Hz), which were assigned to H-4', H-3' and H-5', and H-6', respectively. The relative positions of the two hydroxyl groups in 1a was also affirmed by the expected downfield shifts of H-3, H-5, H-3', H-5' of 1a in the ¹H NMR spectrum of its diacetate 1b.

Catechol, on the other hand, formed a symmetrical dimer 2a (M⁺ 218) in a much better yield (50.5%). It showed IR band at 3400 cm⁻¹ for phenolic hydroxyl functions. The presence of four such groups in 2a was confirmed by the formation of its tetraacetyl derivative 2b with Ac₂O and pyridine. The relative positions of the four hydroxyl groups in 2a were ascertained from the chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of the signals for the aromatic protons of 2a and 2b. The ¹H NMR spectrum of 2a showed, besides the signals for the four phenolic hydroxyl protons at δ 8.05 and 8.13 (each 2H, s, disappeared on deuterium exchange), those at δ 6.81 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 6.85 (2H, dd, *J*₁ 8.2 and *J*₂ 1.95 Hz) and 7.00 (2H,

d, J 1.9 Hz). The above signals were thus assigned to H-5, H-5', H-6, H-6' and H-2, H-2', with the four hydroxyl groups placed at C-3, C-3' and C-4, C-4' of **2a**. This was also confirmed by the expected downfield shifts of all the aromatic proton signals of **2a** in the spectrum of its tetraacetate **2b**.

The reaction of CuCl(OH).TMEDA with resorcinol, however, did not work well and afforded a mixture of two biphenyl derivatives in the ratio of 2 : 1 in an overall yield of only about 25%. They could not be separated even by repeated chromatography owing to their very close polarities. The presence of distinctly two compounds in the mixture was, however, revealed from the ^1H NMR spectrum of the product, which was intelligible in terms of the structures **3a** and **4a** for the major and minor compounds, respectively, formed in the above reaction.

Pyrogallol, on the other hand, reacted smoothly with CuCl(OH).TMEDA giving regioselectively a single biphenyl derivative **5a** in fairly good yield (60.5%). The compound showed strong IR absorptions at 3440 cm^{-1} for phenolic hydroxyl groups. The presence of six such groups in **5a** was confirmed by the formation of its hexaacetyl derivative **5b** with Ac_2O and pyridine. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **5a** showed, besides signals for six phenolic hydroxyl protons at δ 8.22, 7.57, 7.31, 7.11 (each 1H, s) and 7.96 (2H, s) [all disappeared on deuterium exchange], those at δ 6.56 (2H, s), 6.55 (1H, d, J 8.36 Hz) and 6.39 (1H, d, J 8.36 Hz). The chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of the above aromatic proton signals are intelligible only in terms of the structure **5a** for the compound, which is also supported by the expected downfield shifts of the above aromatic proton signal of **5a** in the spectrum of its hexaacetate **5b**.

The structures of **1a**, **2a** and **5a** were also confirmed by the ^{13}C NMR spectral data of their respective acetyl derivatives **1b**, **2b** and **5b** (Table 1).

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR spectral data (ppm) of **1b**, **2b** and **5b***

C	1b	2b	5b	C	1b	2b	5b
1	139.8	138.4	143.5	2'	150.1	122.2	146.5
2	129.9	122.2	121.4	3'	122.8	142.5	137.4
3	121.2	142.5	148.0	4'	130.7	141.9	146.0
4	150.2	141.9	132.0	5'	126.2	123.7	121.0
5	121.2	123.7	148.0	6'	128.5	125.0	127.1
6	129.9	125.0	121.4	OAc	167.9	167.8	167.4
1'	134.8	138.4	134.4		20.9	20.4	166.6
					20.7		20.4
							20.3

*Spectra were run in CDCl_3 and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta(\text{TMS}) = \delta(\text{CDCl}_3) + 76.9$ ppm

The reaction was then extended to three naturally occurring phenolic phenanthrene derivatives, nudol (**6a**), 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene (**6b**) and cir-

rhoptalin (**7**). Thus, treatment of **6a** and **6b** with CuCl(OH).TMEDA afforded the respective 1,1'-dimers **8a** and **8c** in 76 and 73% yields, respectively, while similar treatment of **7** gave the corresponding 8,8'-dimer **9a** in 66% yield. The biphenanthryls **8a**, **8c** and **9a** obtained above were identified by direct comparison (tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectra) with their respective authentic samples obtained by us earlier²¹ by oxidative phenol-coupling reaction with phosphomolybdic acid (PMA) on silica gel surface from their respective monomers. Compounds **8a** and **8c** formed tetraacetates **8b** and **8d**, while **9a** afforded a diacetate **9b** on treatment with Ac_2O and pyridine. The physical constants and the ^1H NMR spectral data of **8b**, **8d** and **9b** also compared well with those reported earlier²¹ confirming their structural assignments.

Excepting resorcinol, the reactions of CuCl(OH).TMEDA with other phenols and the phenanthrols studied above exhibited a fairly high degree of regioselectivity. Although the yields of the products in the above reaction is relatively less than those obtained with PMA on silica gel surface, which was used in stoichiometric ratio, the catalytic nature of CuCl(OH).TMEDA is a positive advantage of this reagent.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Silica gel (100–200 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for TLC. UV spectra were measured in 95% aldehyde-free EtOH and IR spectra in KBr disc. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured at 300 MHz and 75 MHz, respectively, in CDCl_3 using TMS as the internal standard. Chemical shifts were measured in δ (ppm). Mass spectra were run with a direct inlet system at 70 eV. All analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents and the petrol used had b.p. 60–80°.

Oxidative coupling reaction of phenol, catechol, resorcinol and pyrogallol with CuCl(OH).TMEDA : Phenol (0.5 g, 5.3 mmol) and resorcinol (0.5 g, 4.5 mmol), each in CH_2Cl_2 (35 ml) were separately stirred with CuCl(OH).TMEDA (122.5 mg, 0.53 mmol and 104.2 mg, 0.45 mmol, respectively) at 0° for 20 h in open air. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residues were separately treated with H_2O (5 ml) and extracted with Et_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The residues were separately chromatographed. Chromatography of the product obtained from phenol afforded unchanged phenol (0.30 g) in petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) gave **1a** (0.15 g, yield 30.3%) as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 77.33; H, 5.35.

$C_{12}H_{10}O_2$ requires : C, 77.38; H, 5.41%; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 233.5, 258 (sh) and 284.5 (log ϵ 4.10, 3.95 and 3.75); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH-0.1 M NaOH) 243, 284.5 (sh) and 299.5 (sh) nm (log ϵ 4.50, 3.80 and 3.56); $\nu_{\max}$ 3400 (OH), 1605, 1510, 1450, 835 and 755 cm^{-1} (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 186 [M^+] (100), 157 (6), 131 (6), 129 (6), 128 (22), 127 (11), 121 (37), 115 (8), 107 (6), 91 (9), 77 (8) and 73 (30). **1a** was acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine in the usual manner to give **1b** also as a semisolid mass (Found : C 70.99; H, 5.15. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires : C, 71.08; H, 5.22%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1760 and 1220 (OAc), 1595, 1490, 1370, 860, 765, 700, 670 and 600 cm^{-1} (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR δ 1.97 (3H, s, OAc at C-2'), 2.22 (3H, s, OAc at C-4), 7.06 (2H, d, J 8.77 Hz, H-3 and H-5), 7.31 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-2 and H-6), 6.90–7.30 (4H, m, H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6'); m/z (rel. int.) 270 [M^+] (1.4), 228 (12), 186 (87.8), 157 (4.5), 131 (4.5), 129 (4.5), 128 (19.6), 127 (9), 121 (35), 115 (6), 107 (4.5), 91 (7.5), 77 (6), 73 (29) and 43 (100).

Chromatography of the product obtained from resorcinol afforded a semisolid mass (0.125 g, 25.2%) in the petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate. Although it appeared to be a single compound from TLC, it was found to be a mixture of **3a** and **4a** in the ratio of about 2 : 1 from the 1H NMR spectral data of the mixture: **3a** δ 6.19 (2H, dd, J_1 9.0 Hz and J_2 2.4 Hz, H-5 and H-5'), 6.35 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz, H-3 and H-3'), 6.54 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-6 and H-6'); **4a** δ 6.23 (1H, ill-res. *meta*-coupled d, H-3), 6.68 (1H, ill-res. *ortho*-*meta*-coupled dd, H-5), 6.77 (2H, ill-res. d, J 7.8 Hz, H-3' and H-5') and 6.97 (2H, m, H-4' and H-6). The polarities of **3a** and **4a** were so close that they could not be separated.

Since catechol and pyrogallol were insoluble in CH_2Cl_2 , the reactions with these compounds were carried out in H_2O . Catechol (0.5 g, 4.5 mmol) and pyrogallol (0.5 g, 3.9 mmol) in H_2O (35 ml) were separately stirred with 104.2 (0.45) and 90.3 mg (0.39 mmol) of $CuCl(OH).TMEDA$, respectively, at 0° for 20 h in open air. The product in each case was exhaustively extracted with Et_2O after saturation of aqueous solution with NaCl. The solvent in each case was removed and the residues were separately chromatographed. Chromatography of the product obtained from catechol gave in the petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate pure **2a** (0.250 mg, 50.5%) as a light yellow semisolid mass (Found : C, 65.97; H, 4.52. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires : C, 66.03; H, 4.62%); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 227, 264 and 291.5 nm (log ϵ 4.66, 4.57 and 4.49); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH-0.1 M NaOH) 235.5 and 317 nm (log ϵ 4.73 and 2.36); $\nu_{\max}$ 3400 (OH), 1640, 1550, 1515, 820, 710 and 680 cm^{-1} (aromatic nucleus). Acetylation of **2a** with Ac_2O and pyridine in the usual manner gave **2b** also as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 61.99; H, 4.62. $C_{20}H_{18}O_8$ requires : C, 62.15; H, 4.69%); $\lambda_{\max}$ 217,

252 and 265 nm (log ϵ 4.49, 4.54 and 4.70); $\nu_{\max}$ 1240 and 1770 (OAc), 1590, 1500, 1390, 895, 855, 815 and 675 cm^{-1} (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR δ 7.17 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-5 and H-5'), 7.27 (2H, d, J 2.07 Hz, H-2 and H-2'), 7.33 (2H, dd, J_1 8.4 Hz and J_2 2.07 Hz, H-6 and H-6') and 2.23 (12H, s); m/z (rel. int.) 386 [M^+] (3), 344 (29), 304 (12), 302 (78), 288 (12) and 260 (100).

Chromatography of the product obtained from pyrogallol afforded in the petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) eluate pure **5a** (0.3 g; yield 60.5%), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 240° (Found : C, 57.49; H, 3.98. $C_{12}H_{10}O_6$ requires : C, 57.58; H, 4.03%); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 218.5 and 264 nm (log ϵ 4.60 and 4.19); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH-0.1 M NaOH) 205.5, 314.5 and 489.5 nm (log ϵ 4.66, 3.78 and 4.30); $\nu_{\max}$ 3440 (OH), 1660, 1630, 1540, 865 and 820 cm^{-1} (aromatic nucleus); m/z (rel. int.) 250 [M^+] (100), 231 (11), 204 (5), 203 (6), 176 (6), 153 (4), 147 (6), 126 (5) and 89 (6). Acetylation of **5a** with Ac_2O and pyridine in the usual manner gave **5b** as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 57.24; H, 4.33. $C_{24}H_{22}O_{12}$ requires : C, 57.35; H, 4.41%); $\lambda_{\max}$ 213.5 and 243.5 nm (log ϵ 5.11 and 4.85); $\nu_{\max}$ 1235 and 1800 (OAc), 1640, 1510, 1400, 850 and 825 cm^{-1} (aromatic nucleus); 1H NMR δ 7.07 (2H, s, H-2 and H-6), 7.14 (1H, d, J 8.67 Hz, H-5'), 7.23 (1H, d, J 8.67 Hz, H-6'), 2.10 (3H, s, OAc), 2.21 (6H, s, 2 $\times$ OAc), 2.22 (6H, s, 2 $\times$ OAc) and 2.23 (3H, s, OAc).

Oxidative coupling reactions of nudol (6a), 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene (6b) and cirrhopetalin (7) with $CuCl(OH).TMEDA$: To 0.1 g of each of nudol (**6a**), **6b** and cirrhopetalin (**7**) in CH_2Cl_2 (35 ml), was added separately 0.085, 0.076 and 0.085 g, respectively, of $CuCl(OH).TMEDA$ and the mixtures were separately stirred at 0° for 20 h in open air. After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure the residues were separately treated with water (10 ml) and extracted with Et_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The residues were separately chromatographed. Chromatography of the product obtained from **6a** afforded unchanged **6a** (0.01 g) in petrol-EtOAc (15 : 1) eluate. Elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) gave **8a** (0.076 g, 76%), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 250° . Chromatography of the product obtained from **6b** gave in petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate **8c** (0.073 g, 73%), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 270° . Similar chromatography of the product obtained from **7** afforded in petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate **9a** (0.066 g, 66%), also crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 260° .

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References

1. R. Pummerer and E. Frankfurter, *Chem. Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1472. R

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- Pummeti *Chem Ber* 1919 **52**, 1404 R Pummeti E Pirell and A Rieche *Chem Ber* 1926 **59**, 2159
- 2 R Robinson The Structural Relationship of Natural Products, Clarendon Oxford 1955, D H R Barton A M DeFlouin and O E Edwards *J Chem Soc* 1956 530, D H R Barton and T Cohen Festschrift A Stoll Birkhauser Basle 1957 p 117, E Eidtman and C A Wachmeister Festschrift A Stoll Birkhauser Basle 1957 p 144 A J Birch *Chem Ind* 1966 1173
 - 3 T Kametani K Fukumoto and M Fujihara *J Chem Soc Chem Commun* 1971 352 A R Battersby A K Bhatnagar P Hackett C W Thornber and J Staunton *J Chem Soc Perkin Trans I* 1981 2002
 - 4 A I Scott *Quart Rev* 1965 **19** I R S Ward *Chem Soc Rev* 1982 **11** 75 K Wenging and O Mueller *Chem Ztg* 1972 **96** 612
 - 5 H Davis H Eidtman and M Nilson *Tet Lett*, 1966 2491 T Kametani K Fukumoto T Hayasaka F Satoh and K Kigasawa *J Chem Soc (C)* 1969 4, R Ahmed F G Schreiber R Stevenson J R Williams and H M Yeo *Tetrahedron* 1976 **32** 1339 F Toda and K Tanaka *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst* 1990 **187** 309
 - 6 J C Roberts *Chem Rev* 1961 **61** 591 R D Finnegan J V Patel and P L Bachman *Tet Lett* 1966 6087, A Jefferson and F Scheinmann *Nature* 1965 **207**, 1193 P K Dutta P C Majumder and N L Dutta *Tetrahedron* 1975 **31** 1167, D K Sharma and T R Seshadri *Indian J Chem Sect B* 1977 **15** 939 D H R Barton D S Bhakuni R Janes and G W Kirby *J Chem Soc (C)* 1967 128 B Franck G Dunkelmann and H J Lubs *Angew Chem* 1967 **6** 1075 T Kametani S Shibuya T Nakano and K Fukumoto *J Chem Soc (C)* 1971 3818
 - 7 S Tobinaga and E Kolari *J Am Chem Soc* 1972 **94** 309
 - 8 M Murase E Kolari K Okazaki and S Tobinaga *Chem Pharm Bull* 1986 **34** 3159
 - 9 E Mcnellis *J Org Chem* 1966 **31** 1255
 - 10 Y Omote Y Takizawa and N Sugiyama *Bull Chem Soc Jpn* 1972 **45** 1972
 - 11 M Fetizon, V Balogh and M Golfici *J Org Chem* 1971 **36** 1339
 - 12 D W Zones and R L Wife *J Chem Soc Perkin Trans I* 1974 1 L Mertini A Zanarotti A Pelci M P Rochefort and R Hinsel, *J Chem Soc Perkin Trans I* 1980 775
 - 13 W L Carrick G L Karapinka and G T Kwiat Kowski *J Org Chem* 1969 **34** 2388
 - 14 M A Schwartz B F Rose R A Holton S W Scott and B Vishnuvajjala *J Am Chem Soc* 1977 **99** 2571
 - 15 J D White R J Butlin H G Hahn and A T Johnson *J Am Chem Soc* 1990 **112** 8595
 - 16 G Blasho and G A Cordell *Tetrahedron* 1989 **45** 6361
 - 17 K Chowdhury and M H Chawla *Indian J Chem Sect B* 1987 **26** 272
 - 18 K V Ramakrishna K Sujatha and R S Kapil *Tet Lett* 1990 **31** 1351
 - 19 H Martin G Jana and L Jui *Tet Lett* 1990 **31** 413
 - 20 K Yamamoto H Yumioka Y Okamoto and H Chikamatsu *J Chem Soc Chem Commun* 1987 168 C Rosini L Frinzini A Raffaelli and P Salvadori *Synthesis* 1991 503
 - 21 P L Majumder and M Basak *Tetrahedron* 1991 **47** 8601
 - 22 M Noji M Nakajima and K Koga *Tet Lett* 1994 **35** 7983
 - 23 P L Majumder and A Kundu *J Indian Chem Soc* 1984 **61** 142 P L Majumder S Banerji S Lahiri N Mukhoti and S Sen *Phytochemistry* 1998 **47** 855 P L Majumder S Pal and S Majumder *Phytochemistry* 1999 **50** 891